

**WORDWALL AS AN ONLINE ASSESSMENT PLATFORM IN
TEACHING ENGLISH**

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Abstract: There needs to be an adjustment in choosing learning media. If it is still implemented in schools with face-to-face learning, teachers can easily display their teaching media to support the teaching and learning processes. One program, branded Wordwall, is said to be capable of helping students acquire and expand their reading. The Wordwall application is a website-based online program that can use as both a teaching tool and an assessment. In this 21 st century world, English will still play vital roles and gained more prestige in education Students will feel more motivated to learn English, especially in reading, and will have an outstanding learning experience with an intriguing page display with a variety of colors. Additionally, by creating questions with presumed, the Wordwall application makes it incredibly simple for teachers to acquire and customize English reading content.

INTRODUCTION

Technology-based learning media is growing day by day. The availability of these educational resources can motivate students to take an interest in the process of learning English. Even though, fun learning media is required to maximize learning and fun media also technology cannot be separated.

Fun media can also give student meaningful learning. Issham (2016) said that one of the driving forces behind the utilization of mobile learning in education is the growing use of mobile devices by the current generation of learners. Many scholars define online games in learning as the integration of game thinking and game mechanics (Takahashi 2010; Bakhsh 2016; Chapman & Rich, 2018). With the establishment of online learning, schools are required to maintain the quality of their students so that they are not degraded. In their research, Abdul Aziz Fakhruddin (2021) stated, a language is a communication tool used to meet one's needs. Changes need to be made so that the learning process can run well. One aspect that needs to be considered is the use of teaching media that is displayed to students.

There needs to be an adjustment in choosing learning media. If it is still implemented in schools with face-to-face learning, teachers can easily display their teaching media to support the teaching and learning processes. Moreover, in teaching English required a reading comprehension to promote students' understanding. Reading is a necessary component of the language acquisition process. One program, branded Wordwall, is said to be capable of helping students acquire and expand their reading. The Wordwall application is a website-based online program that can use as both a teaching tool and an assessment.

In this 21 st century world, English will still play vital roles and gained more prestige in education (Suhendi, 2017). Suhendi added that learning English in the twenty-first century also requires developing communication and teamwork abilities. Teachers should also encourage pupils to be lifelong learners and focus on their critical thinking and problem-solving skills in the twenty-first century. Furthermore, the illiterate of the 21st century will not be those who

cannot read and write, but those who cannot learn, unlearn, and relearn Toffler (2014).

Students will feel more motivated to learn English, especially in reading, and will have an outstanding learning experience with an intriguing page display with a variety of colors. Additionally, by creating questions with presumed, the Wordwall application makes it incredibly simple for teachers to acquire and customize English reading content. As long as they are linked to the internet network, students are also permitted to use their own devices, such as computers or gadgets.

One of the question models that can be made by the teacher is a question which is limited to a certain time. For example, in reading questions about animals. The teacher can choose a picture of a cow that is already available in the Wordwall application then attach a question, as well as set the time limit for students to answer the question. In addition, there are features such as the original sound of a cow that will appear when students click on the image of a cow and also other sounds when pressing another image. Students' results are also automatically visibly shown, categorized by points for accurate answers, and given bonus points for answering quickly. Students' passion for responding to Wordwall questions may be stimulated by this topic. The Wordwall app is designed to provide students a memorable and enjoyable English reading lesson with a variation in a class.

Every single thing that made by human has an advantage and a weakness. Wordwall is an attractive and colorful media that makes

students always motivated to learn more. The students will not feel bored quickly because even though they are studying, they are like playing the games they used to play. As well as Syafiqah Hasram (2021) statement in her journal, “This game is accompanied by colorful pictures to help retain players’ attention, association of words with images, strengthen the memory of spelling as well as support the understanding of word meaning directly and indirectly. The design of the Wordwall encourages the use of mobile and gamified learning in class as a teaching aid and serves as supplementary material to encourage fun and independent out of-class learning.” The online game integrates thinking and game mechanics to solve pupils’ problems and engage them in interactive learning (Bakhsh, 2016; Chapman & Rich, 2018).

A game-based of its protocol promotes an atmosphere of fun learning. Unfortunately, there is one drawback that we will encounter when using this Wordwall platform. This application can be used in full if we buy and create a licensed account. When we have an official account issued by Wordwall, we will be able to create media with various models available in Wordwall. Meanwhile, when we only create an account for free, such as a Google account, then we can only use a maximum of five game models to create learning media or assessments. Moreover, although it can be accessed every time and everywhere, the application can’t be accessed without an internet connection. But don’t be sad, because there is one solution that can be applied so that we can use more than five game models. We can create more than one Google account which we can later use to login to the Wordwall application. If one account has reached the maximum usage limit, then we can switch to our other account. However, given the various scenarios, conditions, and school requirements, not all of them can or should be practiced.

Especially while teaching English, which contains a large amount of foreign terminology. In Short, teacher still be able to provide a meaningful learning for our students and give some variations with a game-based learning assessment. The perception that raised on the class that using Wordwall as a learning and assessing media can be concerned to make a better teaching process. Andreani and Ying (2019) found that interactive online game has succeeded in enhancing the language learning experience for low proficiency EFL elementary learners.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Speaking, one of the four essential language skills in English (listening, speaking, reading, writing), is frequently utilized to evaluate an individual's language competence and performance. It involves articulating sounds and expressing words with the aim of conveying ideas, feelings, thoughts, beliefs, or needs. Speaking is widely considered the most crucial skill to master in language learning, with Pakpahan & Gultom (2020) highlighting its importance as a key aspect of language acquisition. Consequently, speaking holds significant value as it enables individuals to engage in conversations, share ideas, and exchange information with others.

In the process of learning to speak, the development of communication competence and improvements in pronunciation, intonation, grammar, and vocabulary are essential (Natsir, 2016). Nunan (1991) underscores that the ability to engage in conversations in a second or foreign language is the most critical aspect of language learning, with

success measured in terms of this proficiency. Thus, learners of English are encouraged to actively participate in effective oral communication.

The development of productive skills/output is inherently connected to the development of receptive skills/input, as the two mutually support each other. In this context, the quality and quantity of spoken language produced by students depend on their proficiency in listening to others speak in English. According to Harmer (2001), the learner's generation of language, coupled with observing its reception, contributes to the learning process, transforming output into input. The relationship between speaking and listening is intimate, influencing each other in conversational use. Harmer identifies elements in speaking, encompassing language features (connected speech, expressive devices, lexis and grammar, negotiation language) and mental/social processing (language processing, interacting with others, on-the-spot information processing).

These elements often evoke self-consciousness in English foreign language learners, leading to feelings of anxiety when speaking. The anxiety experienced during the process of learning to speak in English is commonly referred to as speaking anxiety.

Learners encounter specific challenges when it comes to speaking. Despite possessing an extensive vocabulary and proficient writing skills, a substantial number of learners still grapple with a significant issue—the fear of making mistakes. This apprehension becomes particularly pronounced when they are required to perform in front of their peers, generating feelings of nervousness and unease. Consequently, learners who harbor this fear in the context of learning a foreign language may find their studies less enjoyable, impeding their progress in mastering the speaking skill. This phenomenon is commonly identified as speaking anxiety.

Indrianty (2016) considers speaking anxiety a formidable obstacle hindering language learners from attaining a high level of proficiency in speaking a foreign language. Drawing on Horwitz (1991, as cited in Indrianty, 2016), it is emphasized that students' anxiety about speaking a foreign language can significantly impact their performance, potentially affecting the quality of their oral language production and making them appear less fluent than they actually are. This underscores the importance for teachers to consciously foster a shared and supportive environment, encouraging students to take an active role in creating such an atmosphere.

Given the profound impact of anxiety on various facets of foreign language acquisition, it becomes crucial to identify students who may be particularly anxious in the classroom. This recognition prompted the development of the Foreign Language Classroom Anxiety Scale (FLCAS) in 1986 by Elaine Horwitz, Michael Horwitz, and Joann Cope (Horwitz et al., 1986). This scale serves as a tool to assess the level of anxiety students experience specifically in speaking situations.

Erdiana et al. (2020) outlined three distinct levels of anxiety: low or mild, moderate, and high or panic levels. In instances of low or mild anxiety, students may be either motivated or unmotivated to participate in classroom activities. Motivated students with low-level anxiety tend to actively engage in goal-oriented activities and display heightened focus on their studies. Conversely, unmotivated students with low-level anxiety remain undisturbed by their studies and exhibit a nonchalant attitude in the classroom.

Moving on to moderate-level anxiety, students at this level typically experience a degree of nervousness concerning their studies and

exams. They may find it challenging to concentrate independently and often require assistance, particularly from the teacher, to stay focused during lessons.

The highest level of anxiety, referred to as high or panic-level anxiety, is characterized by students exhibiting extreme concern about the lesson, particularly impending tests. These students may intensify their study efforts to alleviate their anxiety. However, some individuals with high-level anxiety may escalate to panic-level anxiety, rendering them unable to cope with the lesson or test even with guidance.

In accordance with Elis (1994, in Indrianty 2016), anxiety can be categorized into three distinct types:

a. Trait anxiety: Described by Greenberg (2006, as cited in Nur Aziza Al Hakim et al., 2019) as a broad spectrum of anxiety not tied to a specific stimulus, trait anxiety, as per Spielberger in Toth (2010, as cited in Nur Aziza Al Hakim et al., 2019), denotes "relatively stable individual differences in anxiety-proneness." This reflects the variances in individuals' tendencies to perceive stressful situations as dangerous or threatening and respond with an elevation in their state anxiety. Trait anxiety is ingrained in a person's personality, making it challenging, if not impossible, to overcome. Individuals with this characteristic are predisposed to nervousness across various situations, posing difficulties in language learning if anxiety becomes a trait (Indrianty, 2016).

b. State anxiety: Regarded as a constraint on and disruption of a person's emotional stability, state anxiety is either momentary or specific to particular stimuli (Greenberg, 2010, as cited in Nur Aziza Al Hakim et al., 2019). This form of anxiety, defined by Spielberger (1983, as cited in Indrianty, 2016), represents discomfort that substantially hinders a person's ability to respond positively to an event or in a specific

environment. It is an apprehension felt at a specific point in time, triggered by particular circumstances. State anxiety is transient, emerging in reaction to a specific scenario, such as learners facing challenging conditions or events that induce anxiety.

c. **Specific-situation anxiety:** Refers to persistent and multifaceted anxieties triggered by a particular setting or event, such as public speaking, exams, or class participation (Ellis, 1994, as cited in Indrianty, 2016). Spielberger (1983, as cited in Indrianty, 2016) characterizes this anxiety type as an individual's tendency to be apprehensive in a specific time and situation. Specific-situation anxiety is a subtype of trait anxiety, manifesting in distinct scenarios. Consequently, linguistic anxiety can be categorized as situational anxiety.

Various reasons can lead to anxiety, as outlined by Horwitz et al. (1986), particularly focusing on performance-related anxieties, which include communication apprehension, test anxiety, and fear of negative evaluation.

1. **Communication apprehension:** This form of shyness is characterized by a sense of unease or fear when interacting with others. Tanver (2007, as cited in Indrianty, 2016) posits that personality traits like shyness, silence, and reticence often contribute to communication apprehension in various ordinary communication scenarios. These traits may even be part of a broader anxiety trait that permeates multiple aspects of an individual's life. Learners experiencing communication apprehension often feel like they are being observed, anticipating judgment and scrutiny, which can evoke anxiety and hinder their ability to speak.

2. **Test anxiety:** This type of performance anxiety stems from a fear of failure. Sarason (1980, as cited in Horwitz et al., 1986) notes that students with test anxiety often set unrealistic expectations, viewing anything less than perfect test performance as a failure. Test anxiety is particularly prevalent during assessments, evaluations, and especially oral tests. Learners grappling with test anxiety may encounter difficulties throughout their English course as evaluations are a recurring aspect.

3. **Fear of negative evaluation:** This involves apprehension about others' assessments, avoidance of evaluative situations, and the anticipation of negative judgments from others. Watson and Friend (1969, as cited in Horwitz et al., 1986) argue that fear of negative evaluation, akin to test anxiety, has a broader scope as it can manifest in any social, evaluative scenario, such as job interviews or speaking in a foreign language class. Learners may fear negative judgments from teachers and peers, causing a decline in self-esteem in social settings.

Widhayanti (2018) identified several factors contributing to students' speaking anxiety in the classroom, encompassing the following eight elements:

Classroom procedure: Students experienced discomfort when required to speak in English within formal settings or faced individual speaking challenges. This anxiety was evident during individual presentations, public speaking, oral skits, spontaneous reactions, voluntary responses, group discussions, discussions in smaller groups (2-6 members), and discussions in larger groups (more than 6 people).

Students' beliefs: The expectation of flawless correctness, pronunciation, fluency, grammar, and overall proficiency in English heightened students' speaking anxiety.

Teacher's belief: Speaking anxiety among students was linked to the instructor acting as a judge, creating an uncomfortable classroom atmosphere, intimidating students, and displaying rudeness.

Self-perception: Students feared speaking in formal settings and worried about being labeled as "stupid" or receiving a poor grade, contributing to their anxiety.

Social environment: Limited exposure and opportunities to improve, along with factors like a loud audience and unexpected locations or situations, contributed to students' speaking anxiety.

Error in society: The fear of negative responses from both teachers and fellow students was identified as a significant factor in students' speaking anxiety.

Topic understanding: Inability to comprehend the subject matter, particularly when using someone else's research as a basis for presentation, increased speaking anxiety. However, when students chose their presentation topics, anxiety was perceived to be less, as they had a better understanding of self-selected material.

Cultural differences: Interaction with unfamiliar individuals caused anxiety among students, particularly when engaging with strangers they did not know previously. In another study by Fadlan (2020), various factors contributing to speaking anxiety were highlighted, including fear of making mistakes, answering questions from participants, exam failure, inability to use appropriate vocabulary, fear of being the center of attention, lack of self-confidence, insufficient English proficiency,

inadequate preparation and practice, poor pronunciation, inferior feelings, and lack of presentation experience. This finding was supported by Pratama et al. (2018), who emphasized that lack of confidence, preparation, fear of mistakes, and discomfort with being the center of attention contribute to students' anxiety in speaking in class. These research findings collectively indicate that speaking anxiety in students stems from diverse sources, ranging from internal factors such as communication apprehension, lack of self-confidence, and discomfort with attention to external factors like teacher beliefs, limited exposure and practice, a noisy audience, and English oral tests.

In accordance with Kondo and Yang (2004, as cited in Nur Aziza Al Hakim et al., 2019), students employ five strategies to alleviate anxiety before speaking in front of the class. These tactics include preparation, relaxation, positive thinking, seeking peer support, and resignation.

1. **Preparation:** Prior to speaking, students engage in diligent study and note-taking to gain a sense of control over their performance. This strategy enables them to plan their remarks and mitigate anxiety when facing the class.
2. **Relaxation:** Students purposefully relax their bodies before speaking, aiming to minimize nervousness and enhance their performance.
3. **Positive thinking:** This strategy involves redirecting attention from the stress of speaking performance by focusing on positive and pleasant thoughts. It serves to bring relief to students by shifting their mindset.
4. **Peer-seeking:** Recognizing the significant impact peers can have, students seek help from their classmates to better understand the subject matter, thereby reducing anxiety. Shared experiences among foreign language students foster mutual understanding of feelings, including fear, nervousness, and worry.

5. **Resignation:** Some students, unwilling to take proactive steps to alleviate language anxiety, fall into this category. Resignation involves attempting to minimize the impact of anxiety by avoiding confronting the issue. For example, a student may choose to sleep in class or skip it altogether.

Pratama et al. (2018) conducted a study revealing that students employ strategies such as rehearsal, relaxation, visualization, gestures (to express feelings freely), and note cards (to maintain control and minimize nervousness) when performing in front of audiences. In a similar vein, Pappamihel (2002, as cited in Yasuda & Nabei, 2018) investigated Mexican-born middle school students in ESL programs in the United States, finding coping strategies like avoidance (not speaking in class), using friends as intermediaries (asking friends to respond in English), and pretending no one else was present. These strategies bear similarities to those identified by Kondo and Yang, suggesting that they are commonly employed by students facing speaking anxiety.

Nevertheless, when students confront speaking anxiety, there are various strategies they can refer to. Oxford (1990, as cited in Widhayanti, 2018) identified six learning strategies that students can apply, encompassing memory strategies, cognitive strategies, compensation strategies, metacognitive strategies, affective strategies, and social strategies.

1. **Memory strategies:** These are techniques that aid students in remembering new information for future application. Such methods have a long history of use, involving actions like forming mental strategies, employing imagery and music, thorough reviewing, and taking specific actions.

2. **Cognitive strategies:** Crucial in language learning, cognitive strategies involve direct manipulation or modification and are widely utilized by students. This category includes practices such as practicing, exchanging messages, analyzing and reasoning, and structuring input and output.
3. **Compensation strategies:** These strategies enhance learners' ability to comprehend or produce the target language. They help students master the four language skills to overcome challenges. Actions like intelligent guessing and overcoming difficulties are integral to this method.
4. **Metacognitive strategies:** Students using metacognitive strategies must actively seek opportunities for practice beyond the classroom. This involves centering learning, organizing and planning learning, and evaluating learning.
5. **Affective strategies:** Referring to emotions, motivations, attitudes, and values, affective strategies play a crucial role. Negative emotions may hinder the development of target language abilities, while positive emotions can aid in their development. This strategy includes activities like minimizing anxiety, self-encouragement, and assessing emotional well-being.
6. **Social strategies:** Given that language involves communication with others, social behavior is intrinsic to the learning process. Social strategies encompass three key activities: asking questions, collaborating with others, and empathizing with others.

In the aftermath of online learning, the teacher adopted a blended learning approach, combining elements of both online and face-to-face instruction. Maharani & Roslaini (2021) define online learning as a system where teachers deliver content, and students engage via the internet using various technological devices or applications. Initially, the aim of online language learning was to provide language learners with

increased exposure to the target language in a personalized environment, allowing them to learn at their own pace and convenience (Yaniafari & Rihardini, 2021).

Historically, online learning aimed to support students in enhancing their autonomy as independent learners, enabling engagement between students and teachers regardless of their physical location. Internet platforms were instrumental in fostering independent and inquiry-based learning (Maharani & Roslaini, 2021). The internet offered resources that facilitated student learning without direct teacher involvement, promoting greater autonomy. However, in the current pandemic scenario, online learning and the internet have become essential components of daily life for students, serving as tools for interaction in classroom activities. The impact of online learning on students' speaking anxiety can vary, contingent upon individual student factors.

Rizqiya et al. (2021, as cited in Maharani & Roslaini, 2021) posit that online learning may lead to heightened tension and anxiety among students during the learning process. This could be attributed to the challenges students face in interacting with both the teacher and their peers. Kaisar & Chowdhury (2020) also discovered that language learners in virtual classrooms experience anxiety, particularly when fearing falling behind or being unable to fully engage with communication models. Conversely, some researchers found that in virtual language classes, students' anxiety about making mistakes is lower than in face-to-face classes, and the virtual setting is less stressful for language use (Yaniafari & Rihardini, 2021).

According to Yaniafari & Rihardini (2021), online learning has created a less intimidating and stressful environment for communication and engagement. They argue that this less daunting atmosphere in virtual classrooms fosters a more comfortable and enjoyable space for learners' communication abilities, especially beneficial for introverted learners who struggle with speaking in face-to-face classes. Additionally, Bowers and Kumar (2015, as cited in Nur et al., 2021) assert that online courses offer students various benefits, including convenience, flexibility, and easier access to education. In summary, online learning not only provides students with the advantages of convenience, flexibility, and accessibility but also establishes a less intimidating and stressful environment, enabling students to communicate more comfortably.

CONCLUSION

Therefore, a blended learning approach, combining traditional face-to-face learning with online learning, was introduced in the aftermath of the COVID-19 pandemic. Blended learning, as defined by Ginaya et al. (2018), involves the integration of traditional and online learning methods. Sumarsono et al. (2021) advocate that blended learning is the most practical choice in the post-COVID-19 era, especially following the partial implementation of online learning. In this approach, multimedia usage in the classroom proves highly beneficial and easily implemented, emphasizing that learning occurs both online and in face-to-face settings. Ehsanifard et al. (2020) discovered that blended learning captivates learners more effectively than face-to-face learning, asserting that the integration of technology in the learning environment enhances student engagement and is more successful in improving students' speaking proficiency.

However, in the post-COVID-19 pandemic scenario, the successful implementation of blended learning is uncertain. Sumarsono et al. (2021) highlighted that the application of blended learning may face challenges, with limitations such as social distancing measures and restricted online media posing potential disadvantages in conducting English classes in the post-online learning period.

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